

Signal & Image Processing: An International Journal (SIPIJ)

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Signal & Image Processing : An International Journal (SIPIJ)

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SCOPE OF THE JOURNAL

Signal & Image Processing: An International Journal is an Open Access peer-reviewed journal intended for researchers from academia and industry, who are active in the multidisciplinary field of signal & image processing. The scope of the journal covers all theoretical and practical aspects of the Digital Signal Processing & Image processing, from basic research to development of application.

Authors are solicited to contribute to the journal by submitting articles that illustrate research results, projects, surveying works and industrial experiences that describe significant advances in the areas of Signal & Image processing. Topics of interest include, but are not limited to, the following.

Topics of interest

- Applied Digital Signal Processing
- Coding and Transmission
- Digital Signal Processing in Communications
- Emerging technologies
- Emerging Technologies in Digital Signal Processing
- Image & signal processing Applications
- Image Acquisition and Display
- Image and Video Processing & Analysis
- Image formation
- Image scanning, display, and printing
- Storage and Retrieval

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2. Accept with minor changes
3. Weak Accept with major changes
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Total Cites	97				
Impact Factor	0.176				
Discipline Impact	Discipline	WJCI	Rank	Quartile	WJCI Percentile
	Communication Technology	0.194	100/117	Q4	14.53
	Computer Graphics	0.074	32/33	Q4	3.03
	Average Value	0.134	—	—	8.78

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Publisher/Sponsor	AIRCC Publishing Corporation				
Total Cites	122				
Impact Factor	0.225				
Discipline Impact	Discipline	WJCI	Rank	Quartile	WJCI Percentile
	Communication Technology	0.521	101/130	Q4	22.31
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	Average Value	0.402	—	—	12.77

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